

ANALYSIS OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL ACTIONS OF VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS DURING COMPETITION

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ABSTRACT

At present, the analysis of technical and tactical actions in the competitive activity of volleyball players is widely presented. For a long time, various variants of conditionally coded recording of games have been developed, which make it possible to record technical and tactical actions performed by volleyball players during the game.

Keywords: volleyball, methodology, theory, tactics, technique, activity, formation, development.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of computer technology, new information technologies have appeared that expand the possibilities for recording technical and tactical actions in the process of games. High-quality computer programs have been developed that allow recording technical and tactical actions in the most complete volume, assessing not only the effectiveness of techniques, but also determining such indicators as the direction of the attacking strike, the workload of the zones in the attack, and so on. Volleyball is a team sport in which two teams of six players are separated by a net. Each team tries to score points by grounding a ball on the other team's court under organized rules [1]. It has been a part of the official program of the Summer Olympic Games since Tokyo 1964.

The complete set of rules is extensive, but play essentially proceeds as follows: a player on one of the teams begins a 'rally' by serving the ball (tossing or releasing it and then hitting it with a hand or arm), from behind the back boundary line of the court, over the net, and into the receiving team's court [3]. The receiving team must not let the ball be grounded within their court. The team may touch the ball up to 3 times, but individual players may not touch the ball twice consecutively. Typically, the first two touches are used to set up for an attack, an attempt to direct the ball back over the net in such a way that the serving team is unable to prevent it from being grounded in their court.

The rally continues, with each team allowed as many as three consecutive touches, until either (1): a team makes a kill, grounding the ball on the opponent's court and winning the rally; or (2): a team commits a fault and loses the rally. The team that wins the rally is awarded a point and serves the ball to start the next rally. A few of the most common faults include:

- causing the ball to touch the ground or floor outside the opponents' court or without first passing over the net;
- catching and throwing the ball;
- double hit: two consecutive contacts with the ball made by the same player;
- four consecutive contacts with the ball made by the same team;
- net foul: touching the net during play;

foot fault: the foot crosses over the boundary line when serving.

The ball is usually played with the hands or arms, but players can legally strike or push (short contact) the ball with any part of the body.

A number of consistent techniques have evolved in volleyball, including spiking and blocking (because these plays are made above the top of the net, the vertical jump is an athletic skill emphasized in the sport) as well as passing, setting, and specialized player positions and offensive and defensive structures.

METHODOLOGY AND LITERARY REVIEW

When analyzing the effectiveness and efficiency of technical and tactical actions in competitive activity, the comparative characteristics of these indicators among the winners and the defeated are of particular interest. Such studies allow us to identify the most significant factors that determine the victory of one team over another. This is necessary to determine the priorities in the training process of highly qualified volleyball players and the nearest reserve.

One of the important tasks in volleyball is the task of determining the trajectory and speed of the ball flight and the ability to timely "get on the ball" - take a comfortable starting position for receiving the transmission, attacking blow, blocking. The ability to quickly solve such problems can be developed special exercises.

The leading role is played by speed and strength in certain combinations. When this is of paramount importance to the speed of muscle contraction and regulation of the speed of movements. Particular importance is attached to spatial accuracy of movements, extremely necessary for the first and second passes of the ball, serves, strikes.

Speed of motor reaction and ability to control time are important movements.

Another distinguishing feature of volleyball is the complexity and speed of the solution motor tasks in game situations. Volleyball must consider the location of players on the court, predict the actions of partners and unravel the enemy's plan, quickly analyze the current environment, make a decision on the most appropriate action, effectively perform this action. In speed play, the degree and urgency solving problems that depend on the speed of the players' actions significantly rise.

One of the important tasks in volleyball is the task of determining the trajectory and speed of the ball's flight and the ability to 'step on the ball' in a timely manner -to take a comfortable starting position for receiving a pass, an attacking blow, and blocking. The ability to quickly solve such problems can be developed with special exercises. The leading role is played by speed and strength in certain combinations. In this case, the speed of muscle contraction and regulation of the speed of movements are of paramount importance. Particular importance is attached to the spatial accuracy of movements, which is extremely necessary for the first and second transfers of the ball, serves, attacking strikes. The speed of the motor reaction and the ability to control the timing of movements are important. Another distinctive feature of volleyball is the complexity and speed of solving motor problems in game situations. Volleyball must take into account the location of the players on the court, predict the actions of partners and unravel the opponent's plan, quickly analyze the current situation, make a decision on the most expedient action, and effectively perform this action. With a high-speed game, the degree and urgency of solving problems, which depend on the speed of the players' actions, increase significantly.

The structure of teaching techniques, tactical actions and the development of physical qualities is an integral process consisting of four stages arranged in a certain sequence and containing specific tasks, means and methods that reflect the pedagogical and psychophysiological patterns of skills formation. Training can be considered as a system, the components of this system are:

- 1 - knowledge, technical and tactical action and quality;
- 2 - teaching and teaching;
- 3 - learner and teaching;
- 4 - motor skill and super intelligence as a result of joint activities of the teacher and the student - the subjects of training.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When building the learning process, the structure of competitive activity in sports games is taken into account, the following components are distinguished in it:

- holistic competitive confrontation in the game;
- team, group, individual tactical actions in attack, defense;
- techniques of playing technique in attack, in defense;
- special physical and mental qualities, coordination abilities;
- motor qualities and skills, functional capabilities, morphological signs.

The formation of game skills occurs in the reverse order in relation to the levels of the structure: -I- creation of high-quality, coordination, functional basics; -I- development of special qualities and abilities; -I- mastering the techniques (means) of playing the game (technique); -I- mastering rational forms of struggle in the game (tactics); -I- complex implementation of techniques in the game and competitions --I- sports performance.

The structure of competitive activity and the stages of the formation of playing skills is related to the classification of teaching techniques and tactical actions used in training; they are grouped according to their educational significance.

The starting point in the construction of the classification is competitive play activity and those specific actions with the help of which athletes fight an opponent in the game. Following this principle, all exercises are divided into: -I- competitive; training.

Competitive exercises include two-sided training games, tactical and technique exercises - in attack and defense.

Training exercises include:

special - leading (making it easier to master the technique), preparatory (developing special physical qualities for a specific technique);
general developmental - for the development of motor (physical) qualities (strength, speed, dexterity, endurance, flexibility), improvement of the skills of natural types of movements (expansion of motor experience).

In unity with these exercises, knowledge is assimilated, the upbringing of mental, volitional and personal qualities.

We present the stages of training and tasks, tools, methods at these stages.

First step. The stage of creating the prerequisites and getting acquainted with the technique (tactical action). The prerequisites for successful learning are the student's motor experience, the level of development of physical qualities, knowledge about the studied game technique (the approximate basis of the action and the main reference points, the main points of movement).

Tasks. 1. Create a conditioned base for training. 2. Form an idea of the studied game technique. At this stage, there is an increase in the level of development of basic and special physical qualities, expansion of motor experience, creation of an indicative basis of action and familiarization with the main reference points. An image, a model of the studied game technique is formed.

Facilities. 1. General developmental and preparatory exercises. 2. Audiovisual media. General developmental exercises are aimed at increasing the level of development of basic physical qualities and expanding motor experience, preparatory ones - at developing special qualities for a specific game technique. With the help of audiovisual means, a representation, an "image" of the reception is formed.

Methods. 1. Methods for the development of strength, speed, endurance, dexterity, flexibility. 2. Methods of visual perception. 3. Verbal methods. 4. Audiovisual influences.

Second step. The stage of learning a technique (tactical action). This is the process of practical mastering, reproduction of the learned technique according to the created image, model.

Tasks. 1. To clarify the idea of the studied game technique. 2. To form motor skills. The approximate basis of the action is deepened and the main anchor points are studied in more detail. The main task is to reproduce the studied technique as a whole, with all the movements included in it.

Facilities. 1. Lead-in exercises. 2. Exercises in technique (tactics). 3. Means of visualization. 4. Funds of the first stage.

Leading exercises contribute to a faster mastering of the technique of playing the game (its structure), exercises in technique are aimed at the holistic implementation of the technique (combining the components mastered with the help of leading exercises).

Methods. 1. Method of dismembered learning. 2. The method of holistic learning. 3. Methods for the development of physical qualities. 4. Methods of the first stage. At the second stage, it is important to combine the learned "parts" of the game technique in a timely manner (as you master it), bringing them to a holistic implementation of the technique. At the same time, the development of physical qualities and the elaboration of the image of a technique (tactical action) are carried out.

Third step. The stage of improving a technique (tactical skill of performing a technique in difficult conditions).

Tasks. 1. Detail presentation, image. 2. To form a motor skill of receiving the game. A deeper and more detailed understanding of the game technique being mastered, which is performed confidently and effectively in difficult conditions, is being worked out in more detail.

Facilities. 1. Exercises in technique and tactics. 2. Preparatory exercises. 3. Means of the first and second stages. At the third stage, the technique (tactical action) is performed in an integral form, in variable and complicated conditions. It is important to achieve the formation of a solid skill that is effective in changing game conditions.

Methods. 1. The method of holistic fulfillment of the game technique in variable conditions. 2. Integration of skills and qualities in difficult conditions of exercise and play at high intensity. 3. Methods of the first and second stages. It is a very important task to form a "flexible" skill so that the technique of the game is effective in changing and difficult conditions, especially with limited time and high intensity (physical and mental stress).

Fourth step. The stage of integration of skills of techniques and tactical actions into game and competitive activities. A characteristic feature of this stage is the improvement of technical

and tactical actions in the structure of complex game and competitive activity, in the system of combining the complex of mastered game techniques.

Tasks. 1. To form a complex image of technical and tactical skills. 2. To form super-ingenuity - a complex of skills with a high level of development of qualities. A distinctive feature of this stage is that there is a further improvement of the skills of playing techniques and, most importantly, a combination of several technical and tactical actions in various conditions of complex competitive activity.

Facilities. 1. Technical and tactical exercises. 2. Exercises to combine the improvement of technology and the development of physical qualities. 3. Exercises for switching in actions. 4. Means of the previous stages. A characteristic feature at the fourth stage is the implementation of technical and tactical actions in difficult conditions, with high physical and mental stress, as well as the ability to operate with several techniques at the level of strong motor skills in integral competitive activity.

Methods. 1. The method of combined (conjugate) impacts. 2. Competitive method. 3. Game method. 4. Performing tasks in variable conditions in the game at high intensity. • 5. Methods of the previous steps. A characteristic feature of the fourth stage: integral conjugation of technique with physical qualities, technique with tactics, reflection of the conditions of competitive play activity. At the same time, both in relation to individual techniques of the game, and especially in a combination of several technical and tactical actions (simultaneously, sequentially, in switching).

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the process of training and improvement, there is the development of techniques and tactical actions from initial skills to high skill in the process of competitions in sports games. The general picture is as follows. The massive, truly national character of volleyball is explained by its high emotionality and accessibility, based on the simplicity of the rules of the game and the simplicity of the equipment. A special advantage of volleyball as a means of physical education is its specific quality - the ability to self - dose the load, i.e. correspondence between the preparedness of the player and the load that he receives. This makes volleyball a game accessible to people of all ages.

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